

Deliverable MS10

Project Title:	World-wide E-infrastructure for structural biology	
Project Acronym:	West-Life	
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Milestone title:	Implementation of a Working Group involving infrastructures beyond the current partnership	
WP No.	3	
Lead Beneficiary:	6 CIRMMP	
WP Title	Networking	
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Contributing partners:	INSTRUCT	

Contents

Contents

1	Executive summary.....	3
2.1	Organization of the meeting	3

1 Executive summary

This document reports on the charter following the implementation of a working group as a follow-up to the round table event that was co-organized by iNEXT and West-Life in the frame of the 2nd iNEXT Annual Meeting. The meeting and definition of scope of the working group took place on the occasion of the 2nd Annual General Meeting of the CORBEL project (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html>). The charter focuses on needed actions to enhance the visibility and to identify common bottlenecks to Research Infrastructures, and on how West-Life can help address such points.

2 Charter

2.1 *Organization of the meeting*

The meeting of the group took place in Amsterdam, The Netherlands on October 26th, 2017. The "Visibility, usage and impact of research infrastructures - follow up of the Brno Round Table" event was organized as a luncheon meeting and focused on the (re)evaluation of the main items outlined on the occasion of the round table event that took place in Brno on May 2017 (described in detail in Deliverable 3.2).

The following participated in the meeting:

1. Serena Battaglia (ECRIN)
2. Susan Daenke (INSTRUCT)
3. Sven Fahrner (EMPHASIS)
4. Antje Keppler (EuroBioImaging)
5. Frauke Leitner (Euro-BioImaging)
6. Giovanni Migliaccio (EATRIS)
7. Francesca Morelli (West-Life)
8. Antonio Rosato (West-Life)
9. Edoardo Saccenti (ISBE)
10. Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel (ELIXIR)

11. Manuela Schüngel (Leibniz Institute DSMZ, WP project manager of CORBEL)

12. Bahne Stechmann (EuOpenScreen-ERIC)

2.2 Charter

The working group agreed to collaborate to target the following items, also with the support and within the frame of CORBEL:

- **Develop promotional material** to allow publicity of all BMS RIs already at the level / by the staff of a single RI node
- **Actively encourage funders** to put banners directing to relevant RI services on the occasion of calls for projects
- **Extend and provide a permanent address to the soon-to-be-released CORBEL catalogue** (update: now live at <http://www.corbel-project.eu/services.html>) to make it suitable for use in different contexts (e.g., from searching partners for applications to calls to guiding potential new users to identify infrastructures offering services of interest)
- **Promote the dissemination** of infrastructure services in a cross-disciplinary manner to the whole scientific community and especially graduate students and postdocs, via personal interactions (e.g., University career days)
- **Advocate the use of a voucher system** by the European Commission as well as international and national funding bodies to access research infrastructures
- In general, **foster the usage of research infrastructures**

